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D5.8 Report on the Ambassador Programme

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Abstract This report describes the FREYA ambassador programme which recruited and engaged 37 ambassadors from 21 countries during the lifetime of the project.
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FREYA project summary

The FREYA project iteratively extends a robust environment for Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) into a core component of European and global research e-infrastructures. The resulting FREYA services will cover a wide range of resources in the research and innovation landscape and enhance the links between them so that they can be exploited in many disciplines and research processes. This will provide an essential building block of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). Moreover, the FREYA project will establish an open, sustainable, and trusted framework for collaborative self-governance of PIDs and services built on them.

The vision of FREYA is built on three key ideas: the **PID Graph**, **PID Forum** and **PID Commons**. The PID Graph connects and integrates PID systems to create an information map of relationships across PIDs that provides a basis for new services. The PID Forum is a stakeholder community, whose members collectively oversee the development and deployment of new PID types; it will be strongly linked to the Research Data Alliance (RDA). The sustainability of the PID infrastructure resulting from FREYA beyond the lifetime of the project itself is the concern of the PID Commons, defining the roles, responsibilities and structures for good self-governance based on consensual decision-making.

The FREYA project builds on the success of the preceding THOR project and involves twelve partner organisations from across the globe, representing PID infrastructure providers and developers, users of PIDs in a wide range of research fields, and publishers.

For more information, visit www.project-freya.eu or email info@project-freya.eu.

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Executive summary

This report provides an overview of the ambassador programme within the FREYA project. The ambassador programme provided a community which the project could leverage to provide input into the project and to amplify the project and its outputs. The programme exceeded the Key Performance Indicator (KPI) outlined in the project's description of work of recruiting 30 ambassadors as 37 ambassadors were recruited from 21 countries, across every continent.

The ambassadors were supported in their engagement with the project and persistent identifiers (PIDs) in general through a range of methods which could be determined by the individual ambassador and their availability. These included webinars, publishing blog posts written by the ambassadors and the annual ambassador competition which funded a place at PIDapalooza or a place at the FREYA final event in 2020. In turn, the ambassadors contributed and influenced the project through the feedback they provided on FREYA services, such as DataCite Commons and the PID Services Registry, and helping to refine and shape them as well as providing translations of resources in their native languages. While difficult to quantify, arguably the ambassadors' biggest contribution was promoting the project within their communities. In September 2020, the ambassadors were surveyed and 10 out of 11 respondents felt they had received adequate support during the project.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Positioning the Ambassador Programme within FREYA

The ambassador programme is a major component of the FREYA project's engagement work. This programme builds on the ambassador programme created in THOR, FREYA's predecessor project, and was adapted and managed in a slightly different way to reflect the different scope of FREYA. Through retaining ambassadors from the THOR project and building on the previous programme, we developed a pool of expertise through which we were able to develop and promote the project's work. The ambassador programme is covered in task T5.5, in the Engagement and Communications work package, work package 5. The description of work states that the programme will be "modified as necessary and expanded to further the adoption of PID [persistent identifier] services and PIDs...leveraging the power of ambassadors as network amplifiers." The description of work also mentions that ambassadors will be recruited to raise awareness and provide training, specifically for end users, and that information, webinars and events will be developed to build ambassador capacity. As the project progressed, the ambassadors were also utilised as a source of expertise and feedback on project outputs enabling a two-way relationship. Within the project's key performance indicators (KPIs), recruiting 30 ambassadors was set as the KPI for the success of the programme.

1.2 Deliverable structure

This deliverable outlines the activities undertaken throughout the ambassador programme, starting from the recruitment process. It goes on to describe and analyse the ambassadors themselves, their roles and where they are from. The subsequent sections describe the activities FREYA partners undertook to engage and assist the ambassadors followed by the activities the ambassadors undertook to amplify and support the project. The final sections evaluate the programme based on a survey of the ambassadors, a reflection from one of the ambassadors on the programme and a description of the challenges and success of the programme as a whole from a FREYA perspective.

2 Background to the programme

The ambassador programme began in THOR, the predecessor project to FREYA, where 28 ambassadors were recruited. The aim of the ambassador programme within THOR was to increase the reach of the project's communications activity and the programme was based on the existing ORCID ambassador network. THOR had 28 ambassadors from 12 different countries. In FREYA, the ambassador programme continued with a slightly different focus and was envisaged to provide a method of amplifying the project. Ambassadors were understood specifically as key to raising awareness and providing training to a wider array of stakeholders than the project team could reach on its own. As the project developed this scope was broadened to a bi-directional relationship where the ambassadors were viewed as part of the PID Forum, one of the pillars of FREYA, which stresses iterative engagement to establish communities' requirements for PIDs.

3 Recruitment process

THOR ambassadors were contacted to see if they were interested in continuing to be an ambassador for FREYA. Efforts were also made to try to recruit ambassadors from underrepresented areas, e.g. the programme was advertised at the 11th and 12th RDA Plenary in Berlin, Germany and Gaborone, Botswana respectively where four ambassadors signed up. The programme was also advertised on the project website, Twitter feed and at various events throughout the project including PIDapalooza 2019, the 13th RDA plenary and the 2019 DI4R conference. The project had flyers (see Figure 1) specifically promoting the ambassador programme which were disseminated at events. The ambassador competition, see Section 5, was also promoted heavily in order to raise awareness of the programme and to act as an incentive for joining.

Figure 1 The flyer used to promote the ambassador programme

Initially, ambassadors were asked to sign an agreement, which was several pages long and had some quite formal, legalistic language. However, in November 2018, after receiving feedback from ambassadors on the original form, the procedure was changed and a shorter simply worded memorandum of understanding was used to capture the agreement between FREYA and the ambassadors. The texts of both the agreement and the memorandum of understanding are included in Annex B.

4 The ambassadors

In total, 37 ambassadors were recruited to the project throughout the lifetime of the project, exceeding the key performance indicator (KPI) of 30. Eleven former THOR ambassadors agreed to be FREYA ambassadors and in the first year of the project an additional 11 ambassadors were recruited.

In the second year, ten were recruited and in the project's final year, five more applied successfully. It was decided to close the ambassador programme to new applicants on 25 March 2020 as there would be limited opportunity to contribute to the project after this date. The closing date was publicised on the website and Twitter and coincided with an ambassador's webinar, see Section 5.1.

By March 2020, ambassadors were recruited from 21 countries, across all continents. In July 2019, the project decided to focus on recruiting ambassadors from Asia, Africa and South America and individuals working in technical roles who were under-represented across the programme. While the project did not reject ambassador applications from other areas, we stressed in communications and when publicising the programme that ambassadors would be particularly welcome from those areas. The ambassadors also represent a range of different career levels from PhD students, research staff, IT professionals, librarians and staff at research infrastructures. Table 1 provides an overview of the ambassadors by geographical spread, function and subject, where ambassadors work in a particular disciplinary area. There was continued interest in the programme throughout the project and the final ambassador signed up in March 2020. This wide range of academic disciplines, languages and expertise allowed the FREYA project to request specific contributions from ambassadors such as asking those with a developer background to provide specific feedback on training materials on this topic. The full list of ambassadors is included in Appendix 1.

By Continent		By Function		By Subject	
Africa	2	Data repository	5	Computer Science	1
Australasia	2	Developer	6	Earth Science	1
Europe	23	Library	10	Humanities	5
North America	5	Publishing	1	Life Science	4
South America	1	Research Infrastructure	3	Mathematics	1
Asia	2	Research support	4	Physics	1
Middle East	2	Researcher	8	Social Science	3
		Funder	0		

Table 1 A list of the ambassadors by region, function and subject. Subject is only included for those who work in a subject specific area e.g. for a research infrastructure or as a researcher.

5 Engagement activities

In addition to regular communications via the dedicated ambassador discussion list, to build ambassador capacity and support their engagement on PIDs outside the project, the following activities were undertaken and the ambassadors were provided with opportunities to present their work to the broader PID community. The outcomes of this engagement are presented in Section 6, Project Amplification.

5.1 Webinars

FREYA's ambassador webinar series has been a key method of communication and engagement throughout the project. These webinars consistently had between 10-15 attendees. Due to the international nature of the ambassador community, these webinars were recorded wherever possible and shared on the project YouTube channel allowing ambassadors, and others, to view the content at their convenience and more than once if required. The number of views on YouTube is provided below, demonstrating their extended reach. One ambassador wrote in email correspondence when asking about a webinar recording, "I watched the last one a couple of times, it was very good".

First Ambassador Webinar - An Introduction to FREYA for our Ambassadors (03/05/2018)

This webinar provided an introduction to the project for the ambassadors and gave a chance for the partners to hear from the FREYA partners and their aims for the project

Video Recording: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=MxqBDMuxc7M&t=2588s>

Views: 169¹

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3361426>

Second Ambassador Webinar (04/10/2018)

This webinar provided nine ambassadors with the opportunity to introduce themselves and a chance to hear from the unfunded FREYA partners.

Video Recording: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WVGeNN8AZT8&t=197s>

Views: 81

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3361493>

PIDs in Use: Collecting User stories (15/10/2018)

In addition to the World Café Session held at the DI4R (Digital Infrastructures for Research) in Lisbon - the webinar provided an opportunity to collect user stories describing users' PID requirements to feed into the work of the FREYA project's work package 3 and work package 4.

Video Recording: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=UFIFrHgtlAs>

Views: 28

¹ All figures correct at 9 November 2020.

Third FREYA Ambassadors webinar (20/03/2019)

The third webinar for the ambassadors took place with a total of seven ambassadors (plus panelists) attending, including Brigitte Hausstein (GESIS Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences Cologne), who presented on her experience promoting PIDs in her network. This webinar was also the occasion to introduce two new FREYA developments to the ambassadors: new PID services (WP3) and the online PID Forum at PIDforum.org.

Video Recording: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=MTpQ_RMYAY&t=41s

Views: 60

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3361491>

Fourth FREYA Ambassadors webinar (24/09/2019)

The fourth webinar for the ambassadors, with a total of nine participants and six panelists attending. Three ambassadors introduced case studies and applications of PIDs in their research and professional fields. Ambassador competition winner, Nicole Kearney of the Biodiversity Heritage Library, Australia discussed the importance of PIDs not only for newly created resources, but for legacy articles as well. Luc Borota from Thunken presented Cobaltmetrics, a citation aggregator developed by their team that collates hyperlinks and PIDs referencing digital objects. The service is creating a graph of URIs which aligns with FREYA's work creating a PID Graph. Finally, Paloma Marin Arraiza (Vienna University of Technology) presented the activities of ORCID Austria.

Video Recording: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8Cl5Vq3s2bo&feature=youtu.be>

Views: 65

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3460655>

Fifth ambassadors webinar (25/03/2020)

This webinar included presentations on the following subjects: Melroy Almeida of the Australian Access Federation and ambassador competition winner presented Building ORCID Collaboration Networks following his presentation at PIDapalooza, Simon Lambert presented on PIDs for facilities and Manuel Bernal Llinares presented on Identifiers.org and JSON-LD metadata. Ten ambassadors attended.

There was no recording of this webinar due to technical difficulties. Materials are available here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4010396>

In May 2020 FREYA started to advertise the project's webinars more widely while still encouraging the ambassadors to attend. The webinars that were organized with a view to ambassador participation since May 2020 are listed below.

FREYA PID services: Graph QL and Common DOI Search (26/05/2020)

This webinar provided an overview of the DataCite GraphQL API and its capability and offered attendees the opportunity to feed into the requirement gathering for the Common DOI Search service.

Video Recording: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=FevVlt5ngPo>

Views: 78

<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3859925>

PID Services Registry (08/07/2020)

This webinar gave an introductory overview to a new FREYA service, the PID Services Registry, developed by DataCite and input into planning for its future as a service. As a result of the webinar a new service was added to the registry.

Video Recording: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=MTM8d0YbfnY>

Views: 53

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3957944>

DataCite Commons - Discovering PIDs and the PID Graph (30/09/2020)

This webinar introduced the DataCite Commons service which was launched as a minimum viable product in August 2020. Attendees were given the opportunity to provide feedback on the service, the most valuable characteristics of it and how useful they found it.

Video Recording: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=zFusYPt-8jw>

Views: 49

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4066391>

Final Ambassadors Webinar (05/11/2020)

This webinar was a chance for the FREYA project to thank the ambassadors for their contribution to the project, to communicate and respond to the ambassador survey results and to give them the final information on the project's outputs and to remind them of where all the materials FREYA has produced can be found. They were also invited to attend the project's final event via this webinar amongst other announcements.

Video recording: <https://youtu.be/kNFefzOweKA>

Views: 3

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4247545>

5.2 Competitions

FREYA organised three ambassador competitions throughout the project in which we asked ambassadors to submit an entry about their work related to PIDs. In 2018 and 2019, the winning ambassador received a ticket to PIDapalooza as well as a reimbursement of travel costs up to €1000, and was invited to present their work in a FREYA session. In 2020, the winning ambassador was invited to join the final FREYA event held in November 2020 and received compensation for their efforts to participate.

Competition 2018

The first ambassador competition was launched on 12 September 2018² with a deadline on the 10th of October 2018. Four ambassadors submitted an entry which was evaluated by a committee of selected FREYA partners (Ricarda Braukmann from DANS, Simon Lambert from STFC, Helena Cousijn from DataCite and Barbara Lemon from the British Library). Criteria for evaluating the submissions included the degree of

² <https://www.project-freya.eu/en/news/newsitems/freya-ambassadors-competition>

innovation and impact, the visual and written communication as well as the alignment with the FREYA work and the suitability for presenting at PIDapalooza. Nicole Kearney who manages the Australian branch of the Biodiversity Heritage Library was selected as the winner of the 2018 competition. She presented her work on digitization of biodiversity heritage literature and to make it freely accessible online and bring it into the DOI system. Particularly, she raised the issue of commercial publishers putting out-of-copyright content behind paywalls by assigning DOIs to that content. Her presentation at PIDapalooza brought attention to this issue and resulted in a couple of changes, including removing the paywalls for specific content that Nicole mentioned in her presentation. Our ambassador competition was thus able to promote the work on PIDs that our ambassadors are doing and amplify their impact by reaching the wider PID community FREYA is connected with.

Competition 2019

The second ambassador competition was launched on 10 September 2019 with a deadline on the 9th of October 2019.³ Two ambassadors submitted an entry which was evaluated by a committee of selected FREYA partners (Maaïke de Jong from DANS, Mary Hirsch from DataCite, Simon Lambert from STFC, and Frances Madden from the British Library). Criteria for evaluating the submissions included the degree of innovation and impact, the visual and written communication as well as the alignment with the FREYA work and the suitability for presenting at PIDapalooza. Melroy Almeida, Technical Analyst at the Australian Access Federation who leads the Australian ORCID consortium was selected as the winner of the 2019 competition. He presented his work on ORCID collaboration networks and a tool in development to help universities discover relationships and networks which they may not know about otherwise. This work applies the PID Graph concept in practice and uses the Research Graph Augment API. By attending PIDapalooza, Melroy was able to reach a wider audience than he would have otherwise.

Competition 2020

The final ambassador competition was launched on 31 July 2020 with a deadline on the 4th of September 2020.⁴ Two ambassadors submitted entries which were evaluated by a committee of selected FREYA partners (Ricarda Braukmann from DANS, Tina Dohna from PANGAEA, Artemis Lavasa from CERN, Simon Lambert from STFC, and Frances Madden from the British Library). Criteria for evaluating the submissions included the degree of innovation and potential impact, the degree of interoperability and scalability, the visual and written communication, as well as the suitability for presenting at the FREYA final event. The winners were Claudia Alén Amaro of Instruct-ERIC and Luc Boruta of Thunken. Claudia Alén Amaro will be presenting a case study of how the PID Graph can be utilised to illustrate the provenance of data produced within Instruct. Luc Boruta will be illustrating how DataCite's GraphQL API has been implemented in the Cobaltmetrics API. Both entries were selected as the committee felt that it was important to highlight the different points of view they represent in terms of PID Graph implementations, i.e. the disciplinary and the generic point of view. Each winner will have the opportunity to present their work in different sessions of the remote final event in November 2020.

³ <https://www.project-freya.eu/en/news/newsitems/freya-ambassadors-competition-2019-now-open-for-entries>

⁴ <https://www.project-freya.eu/en/news/newsitems/freya-ambassadors-competition-1>

5.3 Blogs

FREYA's blog offered a useful light touch engagement opportunity for ambassadors to share details of their work with the wider PID community and for FREYA to share broader information about PIDs. There were nine blogs from ambassadors in total.

1. Historic literature, DOIs & PIDapalooza (04/04/2019)

This blog post is written by our FREYA ambassador Nicole Kearney, Manager, Biodiversity Heritage Library Australia. In this post Nicole shares with us her experience at PIDapalooza 2019, Dublin.

<https://www.project-freya.eu/en/blogs/blogs/historic-literature-dois-pidapalooza>

2. Presenting ORCID to Brazilian Graduate Students (21/10/2019)

This blog post is written by Paloma Marín Arraiza, FREYA's ambassador, who writes about an annual conference at São Paulo State University (UNESP) in Brazil, where students have the opportunity to learn about current research topics as well as more transversal research topics, such as the use of persistent identifiers for researchers (e.g. ORCID ID)

<https://www.project-freya.eu/en/blogs/blogs/presenting-orcid-to-brazilian-graduate-students>

3. Extending the Global PID Graph with Non-Persistent IDs (04/11/2019)

This blog post is written by our FREYA ambassador Luc Boruta. He is the CEO of [Thunken](#), an independent data science company that specializes in analysing documents relating to science and innovation and is involved in [Cobaltmetrics](#). Cobaltmetrics proposes an innovative way to track all those scholarly resources that haven't and will never be assigned a PID.

"With [Cobaltmetrics](#)" - writes Boruta - "we consider that tracking PID citations is not enough, and that other identifiers and hyperlinks are also valid citations...when our users query our citation index, our [URI transmutation API](#) automatically collates citations to all PIDs and URIs known to identify the same resource, whether the cited resource was assigned a PID or not, and whether the citing resource used that PID or a non-persistent ID."

<https://www.project-freya.eu/en/blogs/blogs/extending-the-global-pid-graph-with-non-persistent-ids>

4. Meet the FREYA Ambassadors: George Duimovich (18/02/2020)

As part of the blog series, "meet the FREYA ambassadors", George Duimovich introduces himself. George works at the MacOdrum Library, Carleton University, Canada where he leads a number of key initiatives supporting PID use & adoption at Carleton University, including DOI, author ID, and org ID initiatives. Among FREYA's achievements, George considers the PID Graph as one of the most important project results.

"Freya's PID Graph" - says George - "though seemingly simple from a high level view, is a non-trivial undertaking and the various use cases highlighting aggregation and exposing related research objects would be very welcome. Beyond a compelling role in supporting discovery, I also see the potential benefit with PID graph service integrations for validating the extent and 'health' of the connectedness and relatedness exposed within the PID graph."

<https://www.project-freya.eu/en/blogs/blogs/meet-the-freya-ambassadors-george-duimovich>

5. Meet the FREYA Ambassadors: Dror Berger (30/04/2020)

As part of the blog series, "meet the FREYA ambassadors", Dror Berger introduces himself. Dror works for the Inter-University Computation Centre (IUCC) in Israel. Dror highlights the necessity to assign persistent identifiers to scholarly resources especially because of the multilingual Israeli reality. "As the technological leader of the Israeli national research infrastructure project" - explains Dror – "I am well aware that PIDs are the essential building blocks for sustainable and reliable research data infrastructure. The PIDs are even more important in a three language-three scripts-two directional environment, as is the case in Israel. Our research community operates and publishes in English, Hebrew and Arabic, making it even more difficult to link between entities".

<https://www.project-freya.eu/en/blogs/blogs/meet-the-freya-ambassadors-dror-berger>

6. Meet the FREYA Ambassadors: Melroy Almeida (13/07/2020)

In this blog post Melroy Almeida of the Australian Access Federation (AAF), introduces himself and his core activities. The AAF is also the consortium lead for the Australian ORCID Consortium and we help our members understand and integrate ORCID within their research infrastructure. Melroy is particularly interested in the visualization possibilities of the PID Graph.

"I was interested in exploring the possibility of using ORCID related data to visualise local and international collaboration between the universities." - explains Melroy - "I started working with Amir Aryani and using ResearchGraph data we developed what we called the Research Graph Collaboration Score (RGCS) which looked at the linkages between institutions using PIDs for researchers, grants, publications and datasets. E.g. linking a researcher to the journals they published or the datasets they produced."

<https://www.project-freya.eu/en/blogs/blogs/building-collaboration-networks-using-pid-graphs-1>

7. To PID or not to PID? That is the question (21/09/2020)

This blog post discusses PIDs in the context of ambassador, Muriel Swijghuisen Reigersberg's research background is in ethnomusicology but she works in Research Management at the Open University in the UK. She describes some of the issues with assigning PIDs to content from indigenous communities. Muriel writes: "PIDs carry social significance. Ethnomusicological data and its 'PID-ing potential' for example, are influenced by copyright, intellectual property and Indigenous rights to culture. Data management, sharing and repatriation practices are important ethical issues relevant to ethnomusicological data labelling. PIDs are not just there to facilitate academic career progression, knowledge creation, sharing and reporting on research within academia itself." She continues: "some Indigenous contributors may not want to be acknowledged by a PID no matter what kind. Knowledge may be owned by a kinship group, rather than individuals and PIDs crucially are not names. In Indigenous Australian culture for example, naming something or someone appropriately indicates respect. Allocating people and places PIDs therefore could be culturally sensitive, not in the least due to Australia's troubled colonial and scientific history."

<https://www.project-freya.eu/en/blogs/blogs/to-pid-or-not-to-pid-that-is-the-question>

8. URLapalooza! Muggle scientists develop Harry Potter "Marauder's Map" technology (30/09/2020)

This blog post from Luc Boruta, who also wrote another blog post *Extending the Global PID Graph with Non-Persistent IDs*, describes work undertaken by Thunken to integrate DataCite's GraphQL API, developed within FREYA, with Cobaltmetrics URI transmutation API so the DataCite API, developed within FREYA, can interact with the web at large.

<https://www.project-freya.eu/en/blogs/blogs/urlapalooza>

9. PIDs for historic literature (08/10/2020)

This blog post is a reflection of Nicole Kearney's experience as an ambassador and is reproduced in full in Section 8, Reflections from an Ambassador.

<https://www.project-freya.eu/en/blogs/pids-for-historic-literature>

6 Project amplification

As mentioned in the introduction, the original focus of the ambassador programme was to provide project amplification and the ambassadors did this in a number of ways. However their advocacy through informal conversations was likely the most valuable, yet impossible to quantify. As one ambassador survey response stated: “When I have any research meeting or research collaboration discussion, I always mention the name of FREYA project and its important goals”. After the final ambassadors’ webinar in November 2020, the ambassadors were issued with a certificate of appreciation to thank them for their contribution to the programme and the FREYA project.

6.1 Feedback and testing

User stories

In 2018, FREYA partners gathered user stories from their organisations, communities, conference attendees and the ambassadors of how they would like to be able to use PIDs, the ambassadors contributed six user stories via a webinar described above. The user stories were analysed and assigned to work package 2, PID Core Services, work package 3, New PID Types, and work package 4, Integrating the PID Graph. User stories were addressed through project deliverables such as D3.2 *Requirements for New PID Services* and taken into account when constructing the DataCite GraphQL API which powers the PID Graph.

Training Materials

As part of the development of training materials, the ambassadors provided feedback via a survey circulated using Google Forms on the approach FREYA was taking to developing training materials and provided input into how best to serve their various communities. Those identified with a developer background were targeted for feedback towards the end of the process to ensure its reflection in results. Following the release of the first iteration of the FREYA Knowledge Hub⁵, they were again consulted for feedback at a webinar using the Mentimeter⁶ feedback tool which was adopted into the revisions of the Knowledge Hub. This process is described in more detail in D5.6 *Final Training Materials*.

PID Services - Feedback and Requirements Gathering

In 2020, several core PID services were launched and the ambassadors were one of the groups invited to provide input and feedback on these services. The DataCite GraphQL API had a production release in May 2020. During a webinar, *FREYA PID Services: Graph QL and Common DOI Search*, aimed at ambassadors and other interested parties, they were invited to provide input on this service. During the same webinar they were also invited to provide input into requirements gathering for the Common DOI Search service, a service under development by DataCite, now launched as a minimum viable product, DataCite Commons⁷.

The Ambassadors had also been invited to provide feedback on the search service via a Google Form⁸. While it is not possible to measure the exact number of ambassadors who contributed to the Google Form as it was anonymous, at least ten ambassadors were present at the webinar to provide input.

The PID Services Registry⁹ was launched in July 2020 and a webinar was held to publicise the registry and gather feedback on its needs and features. Again this was targeted at ambassadors and other interested parties. About ten ambassadors attended the webinar and gave feedback on the service. Due to the nature of the service, many of the ambassadors in attendance were those who administer PID Services. As a result

⁵ <https://www.pidforum.org/c/knowledge-hub/11>

⁶ <https://www.mentimeter.com/>

⁷ <https://commons.datacite.org/>

⁸ <https://www.pidforum.org/t/common-doi-search-let-us-know-what-you-think/988>

⁹ <https://www.pidservices.org/>

of this webinar, one of the ambassadors, Luc Boruta from Thunken, had two services included in the registry¹⁰.

6.2 Translations on Knowledge Hub

The FREYA ambassadors have shown their interest in the FREYA programme also by translating the PID resource in the Knowledge Hub ‘Why use PIDs’ into their native languages¹¹. The project received translations in Portuguese, Arabic, Slovakian, Ukrainian and have received 1,418 views combined¹².

In addition to the content of the Knowledge Hub, ambassadors also provided translations of the subtitles of the FREYA video the Power of PIDs. Thanks to the ambassadors, subtitles are currently available in Portuguese, Spanish, Slovak, Chinese and Ukrainian¹³.

6.3 Research Data Canada webinar

On 27 February 2020, the FREYA project was invited by one of the ambassadors, Mark Leggott from Research Data Canada (RDC), to speak at one of their webinars. FREYA partners DANS, DataCite and PANGAEA were involved in this webinar that focused on “the PID Graph and its potential”. A general introduction about the FREYA project was followed by an overview of the PID Graph and how we have defined it within the project. Then, the IGSN scanner, a disciplinary demonstrator developed at PANGAEA, was presented to showcase the use of the PID Graph in a disciplinary context. Lastly, the PID Forum was promoted to the RDC community. A recording of the webinar is available on YouTube (117 views) and slides of the webinar are available on Zenodo (24 views, 10 downloads).¹⁴

6.4 Presentations and event participation

Throughout the lifetime of the FREYA project, ambassadors have stated that they have mentioned the FREYA programme throughout their work in informal settings with colleagues throughout their work. In responding to the survey, described in Section 7, five of the ambassadors who responded, and who were also very active in the programme, stated they mentioned, promoted or discussed FREYA at the events listed in Table 2. There was plenty of anecdotal evidence that other ambassadors promoted the project elsewhere, but they did not officially report their activity to the project via the survey.

Event Name	Event URL	Estimate number attendees
Canadian Data Curation Forum, October 2019	https://data-curation.github.io/	20-100
CANARIE Research Data Management Workshop, February 2020	https://www.canarie.ca/rdm/works-hop2020/	20-100

¹⁰ <https://doi.org/10.25495/912q-yc02> and <https://doi.org/10.25495/gg9m-c669>

¹¹ <https://www.pidforum.org/c/knowledge-hub/pid-resources-in-languages-other-than-english/41>

¹² Figure correct at 9 November 2020.

¹³ The video with subtitles is available on YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9G4EMJCwCw4>

¹⁴ Video recording available here: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=BALSvZikDr8>. Slides available here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3759090>. View figures correct at 9 November 2020.

Altmetrics Conference 2019	https://www.altmetricsconference.com/past-events/6am-sterling/	20-100
FORCE 2019	https://www.force11.org/meetings/force2019	20-100
GFII's Working Group on Open Science	N/A	20-100
PUBMET 2019	http://pubmet.unizd.hr/pubmet2019/	20-100
LATmetrics 2019	https://www.latmetrics.com/	20-100
NIH Workshop on the role of generalist repositories 2020	https://datascience.nih.gov/data-ecosystem/NIH-data-repository-workshop	20-100
MERIL Final event 2019	http://outreach.meril.eu/event/meril-final-conference/	20-100
Biodiversity Next Conference 2019	https://biodiversitynext.org/	20-100
TDWG/SPNHC Conference 2019	https://www.sphcchicago2019.com/	20-100
Atlas of Living Australian Annual Meeting 2019/20	N/A	20-100
UCT Open Data Day 2019	http://www.digitalservices.lib.uct.ac.za/news/celebrate-opendataday-2019-digital-library-services	1-20
EOSC-Life workshops & meetings	https://www.eosc-life.eu/news-events/	20-100
ERIC-Forum meetings	For example https://www.eric-forum.eu/2020/01/23/eric-forum-meeting-05-06-february-2020-brussels-belgium/	1-20
EU-LAC Res Infra kick off meeting	https://resinfra-eulac.eu/	20-100

RI-VIS Communication meetings	https://ri-vis.eu/network/rivis/events	1-20
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Table 2 Events and presentations with participation from FREYA Ambassadors.

6.5 Information sharing

Ambassadors were also able to contribute information to the project to assist with its outputs. For example, Elton Barker who is the Community Director for the Pelagios Network¹⁵, which aims to improve the understanding of historical places through semantic annotation, provided insights to the project team during a specifically arranged online meeting. Barker's experience relates to sustaining a network of voluntary organisations beyond grant funding, which was relevant to work package 6, Sustainability. Muriel Swijghuisen Reigersberg who researches ethnomusicology also provided insights to the project around the issues her community has with using PIDs in the context of indigenous communities, which was subsequently described in a blog post, see Section 5.3.

¹⁵ <https://pelagios.org/>

7 Survey

To gather views on the ambassadors' experience of the programme, the project team circulated a survey to try to determine ambassadors' motivations toward signing up and whether they felt they were well supported throughout the project. The survey was also used as a validation exercise to confirm the activities ambassadors had undertaken throughout the programme. The survey was open for responses between 4 and 14 September 2020. Of the 37 ambassadors, 11 responded, representing a 29% response rate.

Figure 2 The responses to the motivation for ambassadors to apply to the programme

For the question of motivation to become an ambassador, 'Stay up to date with the PID Community' was the most popular response which all but one selected. 'Increase Knowledge on Persistent Identifiers' was the next most popular option, see Figure 2.

Figure 3 The responses to the perceived benefits of the ambassador programme

The most popular benefit noted was “Stay up to date with the latest developments”, see Figure 3. All but one ambassador said they had received enough support and guidance, see Figure 4.

Figure 4 The vast majority of ambassadors felt that they had received enough support and guidance from the programme

Ambassadors were asked to suggest what could have been improved about the programme and there were four responses. Two related to the theme of networking between ambassadors and that there could have been more of it. While the project did try to facilitate this within the project, through discussion at webinars, a discussion list and the creation of a discussion space on the PID Forum, the uptake from ambassadors was low. The list was occasionally used for dissemination of the information by the ambassadors to others but was not widely used for discussion, however the ambassador webinars provided a valuable forum for ambassadors to share and discuss their work with one another. Another comment related to timing webinars across different time zones. This was recognised as a potential issue from the outset of the project and there was always an effort to try to schedule webinars at different times of day enable ambassadors in different regions to attend as well as recording the webinars for those who could not attend at the time. A couple of ambassador webinars were constrained in scheduling to accommodate speakers from around the world, which meant that the timings were not conducive to other areas in those instances.

Another ambassador commented that they felt that the information with which they had been provided was at a PID Service Provider level, e.g. DataCite, rather than at the local institutional level. It is true that much of the communication of services in Year 3 of the project, related to those core PID services, rather than disciplinary implementations, which may have been more applicable to a librarian or repository manager, and were publicised widely in Year 2. To remedy this the disciplinary partner implementation web pages were highlighted and a full description of resources and project outputs was presented at the final ambassador webinar.

The ambassadors were also invited to make any further comments they wished on the project and two expressed a lack of time available to commit to the programme. There was also some positive feedback about the project and its outputs, with one expressing regret it was not continuing.

8 Reflections from an ambassador

One of the FREYA Ambassadors, Nicole Kearney, Manager of the Biodiversity Heritage Library based at Museums Victoria in Australia, reflects on her experiences as a FREYA ambassador and views on PIDs in general. This piece was published on the FREYA blog and has been reproduced here to illustrate an example of the value of the programme to an ambassador. The ambassador programme afforded Nicole the opportunity to publicise her work to the PID community at PIDapalooza, an opportunity which would not have been possible otherwise. Through her involvement with the programme, her knowledge of PIDs has grown and have become a more central part of her role. Nicole's presentation at PIDapalooza was a great chance for the FREYA project to highlight some lesser known issues around PIDs and raise awareness of the ambassador programme to the PIDapalooza community early in the project's second year.

PIDs for Historic Literature

My passion for persistent identifiers (PIDs) really only began in 2014, when I started working with material that sits outside the PID graph: I manage the Australian branch of the Biodiversity Heritage Library (BHL), the world's largest online repository of biodiversity heritage literature.

The PID graph consisting of DOIs and ORCIDs has revolutionised modern publishing, enabling researchers and organisations to permanently locate, cite, link, connect, share and track all elements of scholarly research. However, this PID graph falls apart when applied to legacy literature (pretty much everything pre-2000).

The vast majority of historic publications lack DOIs and this means they are excluded from the linked network of modern publications, either appearing in reference lists as unlinked citations or not at all, because they are too hard for authors to locate and/or cite. The upshot of this is that our historic literature is in danger of falling into obscurity.

The same is true for historic authors. One of ORCID's core principles is that individuals control their ORCID and the information attached to it¹⁶ and therein lies the problem: ORCIDs must be self-administered. This means they cannot be retrospectively assigned to the dead (or to the living who, for whatever reason, have not registered for one). This makes it impossible to connect and track the academic output of historic authors using ORCIDs.

Since 2014, I've been working (with many others) to bring the world's historic biodiversity literature into the linked network of scholarly research and, wherever possible, to use PIDs to achieve this. I started by retrospectively assigning DOIs¹⁷ to the back issues of the *Memoirs of Museum Victoria* (the journal of my home institution), all the way back to volume 1 published in 1906: see <https://doi.org/10.24199/j.mmv.1906.1.01>. I then ensured that these new DOIs appeared in the bibliographic data wherever else the *Memoirs* appeared online, such as on the BHL website¹⁸.

¹⁶ <https://orcid.org/about/trust/control>

¹⁷ <https://www.vala.org.au/vala2018-proceedings/vala2018-session-9-kearney/>

¹⁸ <https://www.biodiversitylibrary.org/part/258161>

Figure 5 Woodward, A.S. 1906. On a Carboniferous fish fauna from the Mansfield district, Victoria, *Memoirs of Museum Victoria*, vol. 1 p. 1-32, <https://doi.org/10.24199/j.mmv.1906.1.01>

I joined the FREYA Project as an Ambassador in 2018 and that year I was extremely fortunate to win FREYA's first Ambassador Competition, which enabled me to travel from Australia to Dublin in January 2019 to attend and present at PIDapalooza, the festival of Persistent Identifiers (thank you FREYA!). This gave me the opportunity to speak about an issue I'd stumbled across in my PID work (an issue that still riles me today): commercial publishers assigning DOIs to out-of-copyright journal articles and then placing their definitive versions of these articles behind paywalls (see *What are we DOI'ng about the out-of-copyright literature?*¹⁹ and *Historic literature, DOIs & PIDapalooza*²⁰).

January
2019

PIDapalooza
Dublin Ireland, 23-24 Jan 2019

THE OPEN FESTIVAL OF PERSISTENT IDENTIFIERS

Figure 6 Nicole Kearney speaking at PIDapalooza in Dublin, January 2019

¹⁹ <https://doi.org/10.5281%2Fzenodo.2547570>

²⁰ <https://www.project-freya.eu/en/news/newsitems/new-blog-historic-literature-dois-pidapalooza>

Since becoming a FREYA Ambassador, I've actively promoted the use of persistent identifiers, particularly as a way to increase the discoverability of historic literature. 2019 was a particularly busy year for me; after PIDapalooza in Dublin, I spoke about PIDs in Sydney²¹, New York²², Bulgaria²³, Canberra²⁴, Leiden²⁵ and my home city of Melbourne²⁶. However, my PID highlight of 2019 was making the historic journal articles on BHL discoverable via Unpaywall²⁷ (thanks to the incredible work of Unpaywall Developer Richard Orr and BHL Superuser Professor Roderic Page).

Figure 7 How to turn the “unknown knowns” on BHL into “known knowns” (Nicole Kearney speaking about PIDs at Biodiversity Next in Leiden, October 2019). Credit: Grace Costantino.

2020 has been a very different year. For the past six months all BHL Australia staff (and volunteers) have been working from home. With our core work of digitising historic literature on hold, I had to find alternative projects for the team to work on. This was a wonderful opportunity to increase our focus on improving the discoverability of our existing online content via PIDs. Since March, we've gathered article-level metadata for over 30,000 historic journal articles and added this data to BHL and Wikidata. We're now in the process of adding Wikidata IDs to BHL's author profiles and retrospectively assigning DOIs to content published as early as the 1700s (e.g. <https://doi.org/10.5962/p.304537>).

²¹ <http://informationonline.alia.org.au/events/alia-information-online-2019/agenda-76401a9b53374affbf95897d17939fb5.aspx>

²² <https://blog.biodiversitylibrary.org/2019/05/2019-bhl-annual-meeting.html>

²³ <https://twitter.com/nicolekearney/status/1106939874471370752>

²⁴

https://figshare.com/articles/Nicole_Kearney_Biodiversity_Heritage_Library_BHL_Australia_presentation_delivered_at_Atlas_of_Living_Australia_ALA_Planning_Meeting_May_2019/8382263/1

²⁵ <https://doi.org/10.3897/biss.3.37356>

²⁶ <https://sites.google.com/monash.edu/2019bsanzalhconference/home?authuser=0>

²⁷ <https://blog.biodiversitylibrary.org/2019/08/bhl-articles-via-unpaywall.html>

Figure 8 Shaw, G. & Nodder, F.P., 1799. The Duck-Billed Platypus, *Platypus anatinus*. *The Naturalist's Miscellany*, vol. 10 (CXVIII), <https://doi.org/10.5962/p.304567>

Working with historic content is hard. The data we need to assign DOIs to historic journal articles is invariably messy or missing. But it's worth it. The historic literature is the foundation upon which our understanding of everything is based; its authors are the foremothers and forefathers of current knowledge. The global BHL community has together made over 58 million pages of the world's biodiversity literature freely accessible online. We're now working to make every piece of knowledge within it discoverable and part of the global linked network of scholarly research.

9 Challenges and successes

As mentioned in Section 6.5, it is challenging to quantify the full extent of the ambassador's amplification effect and likewise it is hard to quantify impact of the ambassador programme on the FREYA project as a whole. However some comments about the successes and challenges of the engagement and its wider impact on the project outputs can be made. Community building and engagement is often challenging and requires consistent, iterative effort, a challenge which has been well met by the project through its constant communication and engagement activities with the ambassadors. The engagement of the ambassadors has varied throughout the course of the project, but there has always been 10-15 ambassadors who have been very engaged and willing to participate in activities at any one time. Reasons for any lack of engagement vary, but according to the survey, they include that ambassadors are voluntary and have to balance their contribution with their existing workload. The memorandum of understanding was deliberately broad with regard to the ambassadors' responsibilities to encourage participation and did not place any specific requirements on them to contribute. This low threshold for engagement resulted in the recruitment of a large number of ambassadors. The project not only exceeded the KPI of recruiting 30 ambassadors for the programme, but also the ambassadors' geographical location, career levels and expertise is very diverse.

The range of activities the project undertook catered to the varying level of commitment the ambassadors could give the project, and the continued offering of different activities helped to ensure engagement throughout. Some activities required a very low level of commitment such as attending a webinar and others required more effort including promotion within communities, e.g. translations and writing blog posts. The more proactive activities could require additional promotion and support from the project team. Section 6 demonstrates that the project was successful in motivating ambassadors to promote the project to their communities and make it more accessible internationally through translations and in a broad array of content being published on the FREYA blog, promoting different aspects of PIDs which would not have been present otherwise. The ambassadors had an impact on the shape of the services created by the FREYA project via the user stories ambassadors contributed, the functionality and coverage of the PID Graph and, especially, their extensive input into the DataCite Commons service. The competitions were mutually beneficial to the ambassadors and the project: they provided the project with a showcase of the application of the partners' thinking around PIDs, particularly in the 2019 and 2020 competitions, thereby demonstrating an external example of the FREYA project's value to the PID community at PIDapalooza.

When it came to communicating outputs to the ambassadors, and more widely, there has been an increase in activity in Year 3 of the project because the outputs of the FREYA project, particularly the range of general PID Graph services, became available in Year 3. In Year 1 of the project it was possible to engage the ambassadors on input into what the project outputs should be, which was done by inviting user stories. In Year 2, while much of the development work was underway the communications to ambassadors focused on the disciplinary applications which were developed in work packages 3 and 4.

The ambassador programme adapted with the project to continue to meet its needs. As the project developed, new activities were undertaken and through the iterative feedback and engagement we discovered new ways in which the ambassadors could contribute to the project outputs. This adaptable approach allowed the project to leverage the ambassadors' expertise comprehensively and enhance the project outputs more broadly. For example, the project invited the ambassadors to translate content on the Knowledge Hub in response to feedback received at PIDapalooza in January 2020.

10 Conclusion

The ambassador programme was very successful in meeting its key performance indicator of 30 ambassadors and comfortably achieved its goal of providing wider community input into its outputs. It was also successful in that the goals and outputs of FREYA were communicated more broadly than the project team could have achieved alone, across different regions and disciplines. The programme should have the lasting impact of a network of PID enthusiasts across a broad range of sectors who have more knowledge of PIDs than they would have otherwise.

Annex A: List of ambassadors and affiliations

Name	Country	Affiliation
Melroy Almeida	Australia	Australian Access Federation (Australian ORCID Consortium Lead)
Valerie Brasse	The Netherlands	EuroCRIS
Janet Anderson (formerly Delve)	UK	University of Brighton
Antonella Fresa	Italy	Promoter
Stephen Grace	UK	London South Bank University
Jord Hanus	Belgium	University of Antwerp
Reyna Jenkyns	Canada	Ocean Networks Canada
Julio A. Martínez Morilla	Spain	University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria
Eva Mendez	Spain	Universidad Carlos III de Madrid
Fiona Murphy	UK	Consultant
Irina Radchenko	Russia	ITMO University
John Salter	UK	White Rose Libraries; University of Leeds
Brigitte Hausstein	Germany	GESIS
Birger Jerlehag	Sweden	Swedish National Data Service
Mark Leggott	Canada	Research Data Canada
Rolf Krahl	Germany	Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin für Materialien und Energie
Suzanne Dumouchel	France	CNRS
Suresh Pannerselvam	USA	University of Florida
Muriel Swijghuisen Reigersberg	UK	Open University

Nicole Kearney	Australia	Biodiversity Heritage Library Australia (Museums Victoria)
Niklas Zimmer	South Africa	University of Cape Town
Mohammed Kaabar	Malaysia	Universiti Sains Malaysia
Clifford Tatum	The Netherlands	SURF Market
Claudia Alen Amaro	UK	Instruct-ERIC
Guo Xiaofeng	China	Chinese DOI Center
Alojz Androvic	Slovakia	Slovak Centre of Scientific and Technical Information
George Duimovich	Canada	Carleton University
Paloma Marín Arraiza	Brazil	TU Wien (now ORCID)
Luc Boruta	France	Thunken (Cobaltmetrics)
Maria de Montserrat Rodriguez-Marquez	UK	University of Surrey
Leonardo Jose Mataruna-Dos-Santos	UAE	American University in the Emirates
Elton Barker	UK	Open University
Victoria Dominguez Del Angel	France	CNRS, ELIXIR and Institut Francais de Bioinformatique
Bachir Chaib	Algeria	University 20 aout 1955, Skikda
Dror Berger	Israel	IUCC, Tel-Aviv University
Serhii Nazarovets	Ukraine	State Scientific and Technical Library of Ukraine
Mircea Zloteanu	UK	Kingston University

Annex B: Ambassador Agreement and Memorandum of Understanding

Ambassador Agreement

Purpose of the agreement

FREYA is delighted to have the support of enthusiastic and talented members of the community and provides Ambassadors with resources and training to support their activities. This agreement describes the terms of the FREYA Ambassador program and provides guidelines for the participants in this volunteer program. FREYA expects the Ambassadors to abide by this agreement and accurately represent the mission and principles of FREYA.

FREYA Ambassador program goals

The Ambassadors program supports and extends FREYA's Outreach activities. The program recruits enthusiastic volunteers who can leverage their own networks to effectively communicate FREYA's mission and support the outreach goals of FREYA through presentations, networking, social media, conference attendance, and other methods of communication. FREYA will provide communications materials, including slide sets, statistics, and opportunities for communication among Ambassadors.

Responsibilities of FREYA Ambassadors

While FREYA will provide foundational training materials, Ambassadors will be largely unsupervised. Ambassadors are expected to be self-motivated, working within their own personal and professional networks to identify opportunities to present, invite others to create, use, and embed FREYA identifiers and services. Within this environment, FREYA Ambassadors are expected to abide by FREYA policies and procedures and external laws and regulations that govern their actions. All FREYA Ambassadors are expected to use good judgment, diplomacy, and courtesy in dealing with the research community. Each Ambassador's work ethic, attitude, conduct, and appearance help to maintain the respected reputation of FREYA. To protect our volunteer Ambassadors and FREYA, and to avoid confusion in the community, please note that Ambassadors are not permitted to do any of the following:

- Indicate that they are "agents" of, "represent" or "speak on behalf" of the FREYA project
- Make news releases or public statements on behalf of the FREYA project. (All such releases and statements must be cleared with the FREYA Ambassador Coordinator)
- Enter into any contract on behalf of the FREYA project.

Within these parameters, Ambassadors are obviously encouraged to speak, write, tweet, blog, etc. about FREYA – and to do so a lot! The key distinction is to talk "about," but not "on behalf of" FREYA.

Ambassadors recruitment and selection

All FREYA Ambassadors must be over the age of eighteen. All prospective Ambassadors must complete a short online application. FREYA will review the application, and the FREYA Ambassador Coordinator will invite candidates for a brief phone interview to determine a) enthusiasm and sincere interest, b) understanding of the FREYA mission and goals, and c) plan for outreach activities. In addition to these personal characteristics, FREYA will review applications for geographic and stakeholder distribution.

Serving as an Ambassador does not create an employer-employee relationship with FREYA. As volunteers, Ambassadors are not eligible for employee benefits, including but not limited to travel or other insurance. FREYA may end their relationship with a volunteer at any time and without prior notice. FREYA

ambassadors may likewise end their relationship with FREYA at any time. In either case, the terminating party will notify the other in writing.

Orientation and training

New ambassadors will have access to a “toolkit” of resources to help facilitate their outreach activities, including standard slide decks and posters/flyers. Ambassadors are encouraged to actively participate in the FREYA Ambassadors community via a mailing list and share information about upcoming events, successes, challenges, and best practices. This list also provides a venue for direct feedback from the user community about FREYA progress and priorities.

Creation of FREYA materials and use of FREYA marks and logos

As noted above, FREYA will provide Ambassadors with communication materials. We anticipate that from time to time Ambassadors may create other materials related to FREYA. Ambassadors should use the FREYA marks and logos consistent with existing FREYA materials e.g. the project website and ambassador slide decks. By participating in the Ambassador program and signing below, Ambassadors grant the FREYA project the right to make such work product available for further use by FREYA partners or others under a Creative Commons Zero license.

Coordination with employer

To the extent required by their employers’ policies, Ambassadors are required to clear their participation in the Ambassador program with their employers.

Your personal data

The FREYA Ambassador coordinators will keep a record of your name and professional contact details. We will use this information to contact you about FREYA activities and events, and your details will not be shared with persons outside of the FREYA project without explicit permission. We will contact you at the end of the project to see if you would like to remain as an Ambassador and if not we will delete your details.

By signing this agreement you give consent to the storage and processing of the personal data stated above. You may withdraw consent at any time by contacting the FREYA Ambassador coordinators.

ACCEPTANCE AND ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

By signing below, you acknowledge that you have read, understand and agree to comply with FREYA’s Ambassador Program Policy. Further by signing below, you irrevocably release and agree not to hold liable the FREYA project, its partners and their employees, officers, agents, funders, volunteers, and assigns from any claims you may have now or in the future (including, but not limited to, claims for personal injury or property loss) arising from or related to your participation as an Ambassador for the FREYA project.

Ambassador’s name (typed or printed)

Ambassador’s signature

Date

Memorandum of Understanding

Memorandum of Understanding (MOU)

FREYA Ambassador Programme

Purpose of the MOU

FREYA is delighted to have the support of enthusiastic and talented members of the community in extending its outreach activities. The purpose of this MOU is to set out expectations of all parties within the FREYA Ambassador Programme.

Responsibilities of FREYA

- To provide resources and training to support Ambassadors in their voluntary activities
- To provide Ambassadors with the opportunity to contribute to or comment on FREYA project reports
- To disseminate FREYA project reports and findings to Ambassadors as appropriate
- To convene meetings for Ambassadors and provide regular project updates
- To subsidise the voluntary and outreach activities of Ambassadors where possible
- To responsibly hold personal data pertaining to Ambassadors (see below)

Responsibilities of FREYA Ambassadors

- To play an active and responsive role in the FREYA project, contributing to group discussions and sharing information about relevant events and best practices
- To accurately represent the mission and principles of FREYA in all voluntary activities
- To use FREYA marks and logos on any materials created in association with FREYA, and to use these consistently with existing FREYA materials (e.g. website and Ambassador slide decks).
- To make any materials branded with the FREYA logo available for further use by FREYA partners or others under a Creative Commons Zero license
- To obtain employer permission for participation in the Ambassador Programme if required

Personal data

FREYA will keep a record of Ambassador names and professional contact details. This information will be used to contact Ambassadors about FREYA activities and events. Details will not be shared with persons outside of the FREYA project without explicit permission. Should any Ambassador wish to withdraw from the project, their details will be deleted. Signing of this MOU implies consent to the storage and processing of personal data by FREYA as stated above.

Acknowledgement

Participation in the FREYA Ambassador Programme is voluntary. As such the FREYA project, its partners and associates are not liable for any claims relating to personal injury or property loss sustained in the course of participation in the programme.

Ambassador name _____

FREYA name _____

Ambassador signature _____

FREYA signature _____

Date _____

Date _____